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Abstract:

This report summarizes the measurement of the ASICs produced in the WP11 micro-electronics work package. The document is organized in two main parts. The first one summarizes the experimental results obtained on test structures produced in a 28 nm node. The second part describes the measurements obtained on complex ASICs optimized for different detectors and applications fabricated in a 130 nm process.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2025

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

This report describes the measurements performed on the circuits developed under WP11. It constitutes the deliverable D11.3 of the work package

The document is structured in two main sections, each corresponding to the two activities carried out within the work package.

Section 2 reports the experimental results on circuits designed in the 28 nm CMOS technology, that was the focus of WP11.2. These measurements were carried out both on elementary devices and more complex circuits, before and after irradiation. The obtained results confirmed that the 28 nm node is very attractive for the implementation of next generation front-end ASICs for particle detectors.

The technology combines good analogue performance, very fast and low power digital logic gates and very promising radiation hardness.

Furthermore, this activity promoted a wider knowledge on the technology among the AIDAinnova community, thus lowering the barriers to its adoption in future designs.

Section 3 of the report describes the test results obtained on more complex ASICs, intended to serve the key detectors addressed in the other AIDAinnova work packages. This was the focus of WP11.3

Five different ASICs were designed and tested, each optimized for a different range of input capacitance and dynamic range. The ASICs were implemented in a 130 nm node and finally produced in an engineering run, which makes many samples of each available to the interested users.

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern particle detectors cannot be built without high-density Application Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs). This will be even more true in future detectors, where all the key performance metrics (space and time resolution, energy resolution, etc...) need to be increased, while the power consumption per channel must be reduced. It is therefore of primary importance that the community fosters its capacity to develop custom integrated circuits. This makes Microelectronics an integral part of a comprehensive detector R&D project. In AIDAinnova, these challenges were addressed by establishing a dedicated work-package, WP11. The work-package was structured in two main activities. WP11.2 was an exploratory study, investigating the potential of the 28 nm CMOS technology to design front-end electronics for particle detectors. While it is well established in the industry, the 28 nm node has not so far been used to design full-fledged ASICs for particle detectors readout. This is mainly because the complexity with respect to older nodes increases, and the prototyping costs are higher. On the other hand, the technology could bring significant performance improvements. WP11.2 promoted a more wide-spread knowledge on the 28 nm process, by producing and characterizing simple test structures and critical IPs. Creating a wide community of users is a key step towards sharing Non-Recurrent Engineering Costs (NRE) in future projects.

In the meanwhile, it is critical that in the shorter term the groups developing new detectors can rely on ASICs to read-out them. This was addressed by the activity in WP11.3, in which complex ASICs were developed using the 130 nm node. To have more samples, the ASICs were produced in a joint engineering run. This approach proved to be very effective, and it can be the key in the future to lower the costs associated to the adoption of a more scaled node. During its implementation, WP11 had to face two unforeseen challenges. First, and more important, the global semiconductor shortage that affected the industry during the pandemic and the following economic recovery. This resulted in fabs overloading and extended turn-around times. Second, the adoption of a legal framework allowing the different institutes to share information and IPs developed in the 28 nm process took longer than initially foreseen. However, the community proved to be resilient and quickly reacted to those challenges, keeping the impact on the time schedule to the bare minimum. This document summarizes the key achievements of WP11.

2. MEASUREMENTS RESULTS ON THE 28 NM TECHNOLOGY

The measurements on the 28 nm technology were obtained through two multi-purpose test vehicles (briefly referred to in the following as MPT1 and MPT2) implemented as mini-ASICs. Each mini-ASIC contains different test structures to explore technology features which are particularly relevant to front-end designs for particle detectors.

2.1. TEST RESULTS ON MPT1

2.1.1. ASIC description

The first test structure is shown in Fig.1. The chip was developed by the INFN groups of Bergamo-Pavia

Figure 1 : Chip fabricated on Silicon (left) and CAD layout showing relevant blocks (right)

The chip contains the following test structures:

- Standalone NMOS and PMOS transistors for static and noise characterization before and after irradiation
- A charge sensitive amplifier to evaluate key analogue performance and correlate it with simulations and measurements of single transistors
- A 8x4 pixel matrix with simple shift register readout

2.1.2. Single device measurements before irradiation

For the standalone device characterization, 18 differently sized devices were fabricated, both PMOS and NMOS. Three different channel length were selected: 30 nm, 60 nm and 180 nm. Three different channel widths were selected as well: 100 μm , 200 μm , and 600 μm . The static and signal parameters were measured with an Agilent B1500A Semiconductor Parameter Analyzer. The noise power spectral density was measured with a high gain amplifier followed by an HP4395A Network/Spectrum Analyzer. The most relevant results are summarized in the following.

2.1.2.1. Threshold voltage

It is well known that in submicron technologies the transistor threshold voltage changes as the minimum channel length is approached. In older technologies, a decrease in the threshold voltage for smaller channel length was observed, while for technology nodes below 250 nm the opposite is true. Called “reverse-short channel effect” [1], this phenomenon is attributed to the halo doping, a feature that was introduced in deep submicron technologies as a countermeasure against excessive deterioration of the device output conductance. For nodes below 250 nm, an increase of the threshold voltage approaching minimum channel length has been consistently observed. Interestingly, this effect seems not to be present any more in the 28 nm process. The measured threshold voltage as a function of the channel length is reported in Fig. 2. Here it can be seen that the threshold voltage decreases with the channel length, a behaviour thus different from that observed, for instance, in the

65 nm technology. The effect is more prominent in PMOS devices. The threshold voltage saturates when the channel length approaches 150 nm.

Figure 2: Threshold voltage as a function of the channel length

There is thus a trade-off between the device output impedance, that calls for larger channel length, and the voltage headroom, which is favoured by lower threshold. A careful sizing optimization is thus necessary in analogue designs, but the observed performance is still compatible with the design of analogue circuits required in particle instrumentation.

2.1.2.2. Gate leakage current

Owing to the thin gate oxide (thickness are in the nm range), the gate leakage current due to tunnelling might not be negligible and the traditional treatment of the MOS as a device with zero dc current at the gate is not fully correct [2]. In the 28 nm technology, a gate leakage higher by approximately one order of magnitude with respect to the 65 nm process has been observed. This can be an issue in those applications where a very long shaping time is desired or in those circuits that need to store analogue information for a long time. Gate leakage current for different processes is reported in Fig. 3.

2.1.2.3. Noise

Device noise is a primary concern for the design of sensitive front-end electronics [3]. The noise of the technology was extensively characterized. The impact of transistor sizing and bias currents were investigated and results in line with the expectations were observed. Briefly, the high frequency white noise was found independent of the transistor width. This is expected because in this technology, for the bias current typically used in front-end electronics design, the transistors operate in weak inversion. In this region, the device transconductance, which is the primary parameter determining the device thermal noise, is proportional only to the bias current and does not depend on the transistor width. The flicker noise, on the other hand, is inversely proportional to square-root of the device area, so larger transistors have smaller low-frequency noise. It was also verified that the flicker noise is independent on the device bias current. Example of noise measurements are reported in Fig. 4.

Figure 3: Gate leakage current measured for different deep submicron processes

PMOS - variable L

NMOS - variable W

Figure 4: Noise measurements for PMOS (left) and NMOS transistors (right)

2.1.3. Irradiation testing

Radiation damage is a primary concern in front-end electronics for particle detectors. Requirements for radiation tolerance are particularly severe for the inner detectors operating at the hadron colliders, where value in excess of 1 Grad must be withstood. Threshold voltage shifts and increase in leakage currents are the typical phenomena observed when a device is irradiated [4]. Both NMOS and PMOS devices were tested in X-ray machines. A dose rate of 5.5 Mrad/hour was employed, up to a total dose of 1 Grad. Minimal changes were observed in threshold voltage values, leakage current and noise, both for NMOS and PMOS devices. Fig. 5 reports the current as a function of the gate-source voltage for both NMOS (left plot) and PMOS (right plot) transistors, comparing the behaviour before irradiation and after 1 Grad. The slope of the curve is not degraded by radiation, while the sub-threshold current for $V_{GS} = 0$ V has a small increase, but it remains still compatible with the design of high-performance analogue and digital circuit.

Figure 5: Noise measurements for PMOS (left) and NMOS transistors (right)

The noise before and after irradiation is reported in Fig. 6. No significant noise increase is observed. The measurements thus confirmed that the 28 nm process has very little sensitivity to total ionizing dose (TID), making it particularly suitable for circuits that must operate in harsh environments.

Figure 6: Noise measurements for NMOS (left) and PMOS transistors (right), before and after 1 Grad

2.1.4. Charge sensitive amplifier

2.1.4.1. Circuit description

A charge sensitive amplifier (CSA) was implemented as a test vehicle to cross-check the findings with individual transistors. A CSA is in fact quite sensitive to device parameter degradation. The schematic of the circuit is shown in Fig. 7. The circuit consists of a core amplifier, around which a dual feedback network is implemented. The two feedback paths have very different bandwidth. The low frequency path compensates the sensor leakage current, while the fast one (represented in Fig. 7 by transistor M_F) discharges the feedback capacitors when a hit is detected. The discharge is done with a constant current. This provides a triangular-like shaping, which allows for linear charge measurement through the Time-over-Threshold technique [5].

Figure 7: Charge sensitive amplifier schematic

2.1.4.2. Measurement results

Fig. 8 shows the output signal as a function of the input charge. It can be observed that the slope of the curve while it returns to baseline is approximately linear. This is sufficient to measure the charge with the ToT method with a few bits accuracy as required in timing circuit to compensate for comparator time-walk or to increase the space resolution with charge interpolation algorithms. After irradiation, the main effect is an increase in noise of approximately 20 %, which is still acceptable. This further confirms the robustness of the technology against total ionizing dose effects.

Figure 8: Amplifier response vs input charge (left). Noise vs input capacitance (right)

2.2. TEST RESULTS ON MPT2

2.2.1. ASIC description

The second multi-purpose integrated circuit was developed by CPPM-Marseille. The fabricated ASIC, shown in Fig. 9 measures 2 mm x 1 mm. The die is partitioned in four sub-chips serving different purposes. The pixel array is a matrix of analogue front-end optimized for high-resolution timing measurements. The SET block is designed to characterize the fast transients that originate single-event effects in CMOS logic. The Ring-Oscillator allows to study the impact of total ionizing dose in digital standard cells. Finally, the single devices allow basic technology characterization, as described for the MPT1 chip. In order to provide complementary information, the tests were prioritized on the analogue front-end and on the ring oscillators.

Figure 9: MPT2 ASIC with the different test structures

2.2.2. Analogue front-end for timing

2.2.2.1. Circuit description

A simplified schematic of the front-end is reported in Fig. 10. The preamplifier has a NMOS feedback that allows for a fast rise-time and a constant current discharge. The input stage is followed by a discriminator with a 6-bit DAC to fine tune the threshold. The bias current in the input stage can be set in the $2 \mu\text{A} - 20 \mu\text{A}$ range. To study the effect of the sensor capacitance on noise, some pixels in the array have a capacitance added on purpose to shunt the input. The area occupied by the front-end is $20 \mu\text{m} \times 12 \mu\text{m}$. The simulations predict that for a bias current of $5 \mu\text{A}$ and a sensor capacitance of 100 fF , the jitter is 100 ps for an input charge of 4.000 electrons and it reduces to 40 ps for a charge of 10.000 electrons.

2.2.2.2. Measurement results

The pixel matrix is fully functional, and it can be properly configured through on-chip registers. Fig. 11 compares the measurement of the threshold dispersion before and after the DAC tuning is applied. As it can be seen, the tuning allows for a reduction of the threshold dispersion by more than a factor of two (from 130 down to 45 rms electrons).

Figure 10: Simplified schematic of the analogue front-end chain implemented in the MPT2

Figure 11: Threshold dispersion before (left) and after tuning (right)

The noise and timing jitter are reported in Fig. 12. As expected, higher noise values are observed for the cells which have a capacitor connected to the input. The measured jitter is higher than what predicted in simulation (150 ps measured vs 100 ps simulated for a signal of 4000 electrons and a sensor capacitance of 100 fF). Further work will be needed to understand if the extra jitter is intrinsic to the circuit or set-up related.

Figure 12: Noise scan (left) and jitter as a function of the input charge (right)

2.2.3. Ring oscillator

2.2.3.1. Circuit description

The ring oscillator generates a clock pulse whose frequency depends on the delay of the individual cells forming the oscillator. The clock is used to drive a counter. Therefore, counting the clock pulses in a known time frame provides a measurement of the single cell delays. In order to save I/O pads, the counter output is stored into a shift register and serialized at a lower speed. The layout of the circuit is shown in Fig. 13. The ring oscillator itself is custom laid-out, while the counter and the output registers are synthesized with standard cells. The ring oscillator is formed by different subsection, each allowing the characterization of a separate kind of cells. In fact, to check for possible transistor-size related effect, cells with different dimensions have been used. Cells with different drive strength and employing transistors with different threshold were also used to explore respectively possible drive strength and threshold related effects. Cells of the same flavors are consistently combined to form an oscillator whose output is fed to a dedicated counter.

Figure 13: Layout of the ring oscillator

2.2.3.2. Test results

A test board was developed on purpose for the measurement, and it is shown in Fig. 14. The measurements before irradiation are reported in Fig. 15. Here the delays of the different cells are shown. For instance, INV0_SVT refers to a ring oscillator in which the individual cell is a minimum size inverter with standard threshold transistors. Similarly, INV0_HVT is a ring oscillator employing again minimum size inverters, but with high threshold devices. As expected, high threshold transistors lead to higher delays. It can be noted that in all cases the delay of the cells remains below 20 ps, confirming the potential of the technology in the implementation of high-speed digital logic. The ring oscillator was also irradiated up to a total dose of 1 Grad. It is important to understand possible degradation of the timing performance, as the timing characterization of the cells, which is fundamental for digital designed, does not consider ageing due to radiation damage. A maximum degradation of 15% at room temperature was observed at 1 Grad dose. This is still within the margin that can be cope with, thus confirming the robustness of the 28 nm node to TID effects.

Figure 14: Printed circuit board used for the ring oscillator testing

Figure 15: Delayed measured for different cells

2.3. CONCLUSIONS

The studies on the 28 nm technology performed in the framework of AIDAInnova confirmed that the 28 nm node is very attractive for the implementation of next generation ASICs for particle detectors. In fact, despite some limitations due to more stringent layout design rules, the technology remains fully suitable for implementing critical analogue blocks such as input amplifiers. The circuit density is greatly increased for both digital and analogue circuits, paving the way to the design, for instance, of new generation pixel detectors with reduced pitch. The very high speed of digital gates allows for more functionality with higher speed directly embedded on the front-end ASICs. The very short delays of basic digital gates are key to implement compact high-resolution Time-to-Digital Converters, which are fundamental building blocks in electronics for timing detectors. Due to the reduced gate capacitance, lower power circuits can be designed. It must also be stressed that, in addition to the characterization work performed, a fundamental outcome of the project was to stimulate the adoption of the technology across the participating groups, allowing the designers to gain the skills necessary for its productive use in future projects.

3. MEAUREMENTS OF 130 NM CHIP

Five chips from the AIDA-INNOVA partners have been submitted in a 130 nm engineering run “AIDA run” in 2023, which constituted Milestone MS46. They are EICROC0, FLAXE, LIROC, PSIROC and CPROC and constituted 22% of the reticle area and cost.

Layout Draft of E-ITO-TMSS02-001

(As of 2023-08-08 21:50:08 GMT+8)

Figure 2 : view of the reticle of the AIDA-INNOVA engineering run

3.1. EICROC0

3.1.1. ASIC description

EICROC is a system-on-chip designed in CMOS 130 nm technology with the goal to provide precise charge and timing information when sensing a particle collision on the AC-LGAD sensor. A combination of an analogue front-end along with a digital back-end allows us to have the desired performance : the architecture of EICROC is based on ALTIROC, designed for reading out DC-LGAD sensors in the ATLAS experiment~ []{b} as well as HGCROC, designed for reading out SiPM sensors in the CMS experiment~ []{c}.

The final version of the EICROC ASIC will comply with the following specifications :

- 32x32 channel array
- power consumption of ~1 mW per channel
- charge detection in the range of 1 to 50 fC
- timing jitter performance between 15-20 ps
- input capacitance in the range of 1 to 3 pF

The EICROC0 ASIC is a first prototype used for sensor characterization with pixelated AC-LGAD sensors : the ASIC presents a 4x4 channel layout which uses ~2 mW per channel.

The analogue front-end of the ASIC can be divided in 3 main parts :

- a fast, low-noise trans-impedance 1 GHz preamplifier
- a fast path for time measurement, composed of a discriminator and 10-bit TDC which outputs the Time of Arrival (ToA) with a 25 ps accuracy
- a slow path for charge measurement, composed of an integrator and an 8-bit 40MHz SAR ADC which outputs the amplitude of the input charge

Each channel also has additional DACs used to change locally the discriminator threshold and the integrator DC level.

When the input signal exceeds the discriminator threshold, an acquisition window opens and data from the ADC, TDC and discriminator are stored and automatically read out. Each pixel sends parallel digitized data of the ADC and the TOA for each clock cycle (40 MHz). If the window acquisition is active, the pixel stores this data into a circular buffer with a depth of 8 : 8 data points are taken for a

single input value. When a read-out signal is applied, the stored pixel data are daisy-chained and read out through a single output.

The following section presents the performance of the ASIC in both standalone operation and in conjunction with AC-LGAD sensors.

3.1.2. Measurement results

EICROC0 is measured in two configurations : one with the ASIC alone and another with the ASIC wire-bonded to a pixelated AC-LGAD sensor. The ASIC alone has an additional 750 fF capacitance at its input to emulate a sensor load, while the other configuration presents the input capacitance of the AC-LGAD sensor. Measurements are presented for channel 0 of the ASIC.

3.1.2.1. Trigger efficiency (s-curves)

The first step when realizing measurements on the ASIC is to use local correction DACs to set all channels to the same discriminator threshold to detect the same injected charge. Correction DACs located in each channel allow us to adjust the global discriminator threshold value locally. After correction, we can expect all channels to be within ± 2 DACu of the chosen global threshold value (initial variation is around ± 25 DACu). This result is represented in the S-Curves of Figure 3 . S-Curves are obtained by plotting the discriminator trigger efficiency for a charge of 5 fC while scanning the threshold value.

After correcting all channels, we can set the global threshold value and sweep the input injected charge to check the minimum detected charge as well as noise values for the ASIC with and without sensor. This value was set at 300 DACu for the ASIC alone and 340 DACu for the ASIC with an AC-LGAD sensor.

Figure 3 : s-curves of EICROC0 before and after threshold tuning

The ASIC + AC-LGAD configuration presents degraded minimum charge and noise values, which can be linked to the additional input capacitance presented by the sensor.

3.1.2.2. TDC jitter

After obtaining the minimum threshold value required to generate a trigger, we can use this value to assess the TDC jitter performance. By setting the threshold value at the minimum detected charge for the ASIC tested, the jitter is measured by sweeping the input charge value. The results are shown in Figure 4

Performance of the ASIC with AC-LGAD configuration is degraded, as the additional capacitance from the sensor degrades the jitter values. The jitter performance is promising for the ASIC in both configurations, as the final specifications aim for a timing jitter around 15-20 ps.

Figure 4 : jitter as a function of the input charge

3.1.2.3. Charge measurement

Slow path measurements are obtained by measuring the performance of the 8-bit SAR ADC. Signal amplitude as well as residuals are plotted with respect to the input charge in Figure 5. As described earlier, 8 ADC data points are taken for a single event. The ADC thus digitizes the entire charge pulse : by taking the maximal value of the 8 data samples, we obtain the ADC value corresponding to the input charge. Plotting the maximal value of the ADC with respect to the input charge allows us to have an ADC linearity plot.

Figure 5 : charge linearity measurement and residuals

ADC results are excellent, with residuals around 0.1% for the entire input charge range, which allows for a very precise digitization of the input charge signal.

3.1.3. Conclusion

EICROC0 is a test beam prototype used for sensor characterization with pixelated AC-LGAD sensors. The initial performance of the ASIC alone is promising and will be improved with further iterations.

Future versions will focus on improving the testability of the ASIC, as well as efforts to reduce power consumption by modifying the ADC architecture in a next iteration.

The EICROC1 design will present larger dimensions (8x32) to test for floor planning and power distribution issues. Both versions will be submitted by the end of 2024.

3.2. FLAXE

3.2.1. ASIC description

The FLAXE block diagram is shown in Figure 6. The ASIC comprises 32 mixed-mode channels, a digital back-end, an internal biasing circuitry, and a calibration pulse generator [5].

Figure 6: block diagram of FLAXE ASIC

The mixed-mode channel, presented in Figure 7, consists of a charge-sensitive amplifier (CSA) with two programmable gains, one for a MIP sensitivity and a linear range up to around 40 MIP, and the other extending the dynamic range to around 1250 MIPs. The CSA is followed by a fully differential pole-zero cancellation circuit and CR-RC shaper with a nominal 50 ns peaking time, based on the fully differential amplifier originally developed for the IpGBT ASIC. The analogue part is complemented by a DAC for fine per-channel pedestal trimming and Krummenacher feedback circuitry, providing sensor leakage compensation as well as preamplifier DC output voltage shift, which allows for an extended dynamic range for the CSA negative output pulses, while retaining the NMOS input transistor for better noise and bandwidth performance. This voltage shift is programmable, allowing for a coarse, global per-chip pedestal setting. The shaper output is digitised in each channel using a 10-bit SAR ADC, operating at 20 MSps sampling rate, matched to the peaking time of the shaper, as required by the signal reconstruction procedure.

Figure 7 : schematic of one mixed-mode channel

Due to the extremely low bunch-crossing (BX) rate of the experiment, the digital back-end comprises an on-chip DAQ system based on an internal RAM, collecting 64 consecutive ADC samples from all 32 channels around each BX. Although the 10-bit ADC is currently being used, the channel data has been already extended to 12-bit, since in the next stage of the LUXE experiment an evolution of the FLAXE ASIC is foreseen to cover even larger dynamic range expected for higher laser intensity. Therefore a 64, 384 b (32 \times 12 b) words are stored in the internal RAM for each BX. The collected data is read out between BX using a custom communication protocol, based on SPI in the physical layer and I²C in the logical layer. This synergy was chosen to meet the specific requirements of the ECAL-p and LUXE design. The SPI physical layer, in combination with differential drivers, provides sufficient signal integrity for communication with a central DAQ system located up to 100 m away from the detector. The logical layer, based on the I²C protocol, provides ASIC addressing, which allows multiple ASIC to be connected to a common data bus, reducing the number of connections to the central DAQ. The same protocol is used to access the configuration registers for ASIC programming. Additionally, to reduce power consumption, a sleep mode has been added in which the mixed mode domain is automatically powered down between BX. This feature can be disabled, keeping the mixed-mode domain constantly powered on for test purposes.

3.2.2. Measurement results

Around 1000 ASIC, as required by ECAL-p demand, were fabricated in 130 nm CMOS technology. The die area is 4045 x 3725 μm^2 , while a single mixed-mode channel occupies 2800 x 85 μm^2 . To meet the detector geometrical constraints, a 128-lead LQFP package, with 0.4 mm lead pitch and a thickness below 1.6 mm, was selected. The first batch of 142 ASIC was packaged and qualification tests were performed in mid-2024. To confidently declare the ASIC fully functional, the qualification procedure performs a complete set of measurements under nominal environmental conditions. For the digital back-end, the configuration registers are tested by writing (and reading back) all possible values, while RAM and the data path are tested using dedicated test modes, replacing the actual ADC data with previously known values. The ASIC power consumption is measured, both in sleep mode and in continuous awake mode. Finally, the analogue front-end is tested by measuring each channel's nominal pedestal and noise, trimming DAC response, pulse shape, and peaking time, as well as linear range and gain. The last measurements are made using an external signal generator that provides a

voltage step, converted to a sensor-like current signal via a capacitor connected in series to the front-end input. This setup enables precise shaper response measurement by shifting the phase of the injected signal relative to the ADC sampling clock by sub-ns steps, effectively providing ADC samples of the shaper response at intervals equal to these phase shifts.

Figure 8: measured DAC linearity and uniformity

Unfortunately, for the first batch of FLAXE ASIC an absolutely catastrophic yield of 5% was obtained. Approximately 95% of ASIC suffer from extreme current consumption in at least one of the power domains, with 35% of the entire batch consuming over 700-800 mA rendering them completely unusable. 60% consume 10 to 20 times more than nominal power, and although these ASIC are at least partially operational, extreme overcurrent significantly affects their performance. In particular, the IR drop in the digital power distribution grid manifests itself as numerous bit errors in the DAQ RAM, making it impossible to read the ADC data. Although this issue is still under investigation, many clues point to a failure of the manufacturing process. The excess current consumption acts as pure leakage, being completely independent of the activity of the ASIC, e.g., the presence of the main clock, the ASIC configuration or the applied sleep mode. The most affected part is the ADC supply domain, which was reused from the FLAXE predecessor, the FLAME ASIC, and thus was already silicon proven. In addition to the packaged ASIC, several bare dies were also received from the manufacturer. Some of these were tested for current consumption and were found to behave exactly the same as the packaged ones, eliminating the packaging as a possible failure point. The bare dies were examined with an infrared camera, clearly showing extreme power dissipation at the silicon level, under the metallisation, mainly in areas where thick silicon oxide was used for power supply decoupling capacitors and IO ESD structures (both already also silicon proven), which may pin-point failure. Due to these problems, only seven ASIC were found to be working quite well, although even these had a few dead channels. Furthermore, several ASIC showed few enough RAM errors to allow mixed-mode channel testing, resulting in 386 channels tested for nominal pedestal and noise and around 190 for pulse shape and gain.

Figure 9: shaper output waveforms and peaking time uniformity

The linearity measurement result of a single ASIC and the gain spread are shown in Figure 9. Only the high gain of the CSA was measured as the primary point of interest for the initial ECAL-p development, leaving the low gain for a more detailed characterisation in the future. Again, both results agree almost perfectly with the simulations, showing an average gain of 3.94 LSB/fC (1.5 % lower than simulated) and a linear range as expected from the simulations.

In selected ASICs that did not have an excessive overcurrent, it was possible to estimate the power consumption of individual domains.

With the mixed-mode domain being constantly powered on, the ASIC consumes a total 71 mW (2.2 mW per channel), with 37 mW (1.2 mW per channel) contributed by the analogue front-end, 12 mW (375 μ W per channel) by the ADC domain, and 22 mW (690 μ W) by the digital domain. In sleep mode, the power consumption of the front-end and ADC domains drops below measurable level, resulting in a total ASIC consumption of 19 mW (600 μ W per channel) coming solely from the digital domain.

Figure 10: linearity of response for all channels and gain uniformity

3.2.3. Conclusion

The SOC readout ASIC, dedicated to the ECAL-p detector for the LUXE experiment, has been designed and fabricated. A first batch of 142 ASIC has been packaged and tested. Unfortunately, during the measurements, a catastrophic yield of 5 % was found. The most likely reason for this is an error in the manufacturing process, which has resulted in extremely high leakage currents being measured in most ASIC. Due to this problem, the dicing and packaging of the remaining wafers was cancelled. All working and measurable channels were characterised during qualification tests, showing performance and parameters perfectly in line with both the specification and simulations. The huge power consumption issue is currently being investigated in detail before the design is resubmitted for another run, as measurements of the working ASIC show that the design is perfectly suited for the ECAL-p requirements.

3.3. LIROC

3.3.1. ASIC description

LIROC ASIC is designed in TSMC 130nm CM013G. This technology has been qualified by CERN for its excellent radiation hardness over total irradiation dose.

Block scheme of LIROC is shown in.

LIROC is a 64-channel front-end ASIC designed to readout silicon photo-multipliers (SiPM) for LIDAR application.

LIROC allows triggering down to 1/3 p.e. and provides low-voltage differential trigger output for each channel with an excellent timing resolution (better than 20ps FWHM) and excellent double-peak separation (100% efficiency on 5ns separated single photoelectrons). LIROC allows fast single photon counting over 100MHz per channel.

Figure 11: block diagram of LIROC ASIC

An adjustment of the SiPM high-voltage (gain) is possible using a channel-by-channel 6-bit DAC connected to the ASIC inputs. Channel-by-channel calibration on the trigger threshold is also possible thanks to 7-bit DACs. LIROC can be calibrated using the dark noise of the SiPM.

LIROC features a GHz measurement line composed of an RF preamplifier with pole zero cancellation followed by a fast discriminator and low swing LVDS fast driver. LIROC simulated performances and main features are presented in the table below :

Detector Read-Out	SiPM, SiPM array
Number of Channels	64
Signal Polarity	Positive or Negative (selectable ASIC-wise)
Sensitivity	Trigger on 1/3 of photo-electron
Timing Resolution	Better than 20 ps FWHM on single photo-electron Better than 5ns double-peak separation on single photo-electron
Dynamic Range	Over 100MHz photon counting rate

Packaging & Dimension	BGA 20x20 mm ² Flip-Chip low inductance packaging technology
Power Consumption	210mW (TBC) – Supply voltage : 1.2 V
Inputs	64 analogue inputs with independent SiPM HV adjustments
Outputs	64 LVDS triggers
Internal Programmable Features (I2C)	64 HV adjustment for SiPM (64 x 6 bit), trigger threshold programming (10bits), 64 x 7 bit channel-wise threshold adjustment, ASIC-wise polarity selector, preamp gain adjustment, individual trigger masking and cell powering.

3.3.2. Measurement results

SPTR measurements of LIROC have been performed against an LYSO:Ce,Ca reference detector coupled with the HF readout using several SiPMs from various manufacturers. Exposed to Cherenkov radiation by coupling the DUT SiPM to a black-painted EPIC PbF₂ 2 × 2 × 3mm³, the timing difference between the reference detector and the ASIC chip triggers on single-photon events is studied. The HF reference readout is set up with a Broadcom AFBR-S4N33C013 SiPM coupled to a TAC LYSO:Ce,Ca crystal of 2 × 2 × 3mm³. All SPTR values stated in this study have been corrected for the HF reference readout CTR. It should be mentioned that electronic noise was not subtracted for these measurements.

Figure 12 shows the SPTR measurement of LIROC with FBK NUV-HD-LF M3 SiPM against the HF reference detector. On the left is shown the time delay histogram, where all events are presented in blue, single p.e. selected events in orange, and exponentially modified Gaussian fit in red. On the right is shown the measured SPTR of Liroc as a function of SiPM bias voltage (HV). The best SPTR achieved is 90 ps (FWHM) at a bias voltage of 39V.

Figure 12: single photon time resolution (SPTR) of LIROC ASIC

It is important to note that the values of SPTR as a function of bias voltage are plotted for a constant discriminating threshold selected by optimizing it for each bias voltage setting that gives the best timing performance for each device. Such a chosen discrimination threshold value corresponds to about half the p.e. level at that setting.

3.4. PSIROC

3.4.1. ASIC description

The block diagram of PSIROC is shown in Figure 13. A charge pre-amplifier integrates the input current from the detector with a feedback capacitor that can be trimmed from 125 fF to 8 pF. The output signal is distributed along four paths:

1. a fast shaper and discriminator to trigger the acquisition;
2. a direct discriminator output for Time Over Threshold (TOT) operations on the pre-amplifier;
3. a high gain slow shaper followed by a peak sensing cell for high SNR charge measurements;
4. a low gain slow shaper followed by a peak sensing cell to handle the full output range from the pre-amplifier.

Pre-amplifier gain and shaping times are adjustable per channel alongside threshold calibration. A discriminator is also available on the low gain slow shaper output to do charge veto. The ASIC embeds a delay box to generate a ‘hold’ signal for the DAQ, all voltage references are generated inside the ASIC thanks to a bandgap reference. The ASIC is auto triggered but an external trigger can be fed through the `trig_ext` pin for topological trigger applications or any other needs. PSIROC aims to be as generic and configurable as possible to fit as many needs as possible. This ASIC is pin-to-pin compatible with the new generation of read-out chips at Weeroc, the generIC family (RADIROC, LIROC, POPROC, TEMPOROC and PSIROC).

Figure 13: schematic diagram of PSIROC ASIC

3.4.2. Simulated performance

PSIROC has been designed to target detector capacitances ranging from 0 to hundreds of pF. Equivalent Noise Charge (ENC) at high gain slow shaper output has been simulated to be under 500 e⁻ RMS for $C_d/C_f = 20 \text{ pF}/1 \text{ pF}$ with $\tau_{sh} > 100 \text{ ns}$ (see Fig. 2.). The fast shaper ($\tau = 40 \text{ ns}$) and discriminator have been simulated to be able to trigger on sub-fC signals with a SNR over 10.

Figure 14: ENC as a function of shaping time with $C_d = 20 \text{ pF}$ and $C_f = 125 \text{ fF}$ (red) to 8 pF (grey). Solid line: positive input; dotted line: negative input. The discontinuity is due to the shaping time LSB toggling from 20 ns to 200 ns

The ASIC has been designed to handle GEM sparks through a custom ESD protection and is expected to handle up to 4 A of peak current ($< 1 \mu\text{s}$), the bottleneck being the vias between

pads and ESD protection. The ASIC main features are described in Table 1.

3.4.3. Measurements

Measurements have been performed using a dedicated evaluation board with a custom Ironwood ASIC socket. ENC have been measured at peak detector output using an external ADC resulting in 573 e⁻ RMS for Cd/Cf = 10 pF/250 fF with $\tau_{sh} = 300$ ns (see Figure 15). This measurement allowed to validate the full acquisition chain. Every block of the ASIC is behaving as expected. Better results are expected when evaluation boards with soldered ASIC will be tested.

Figure 15: High gain shaper output amplitude with input charge = 5 fC and 10 fC, Cd = 10 pF, Cf = 250 fF, $\tau_{sh} = 200$ ns. Standard deviation is 3.2 mV, signal pedestal is 100 mV, giving an SNR for 10 fC $(450-100)/3.2 = 109$ and ENC = $10 \text{ fC}/109/1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} = 573 \text{ e}^- \text{ RMS}$.

3.4.4. Conclusion

Evaluation boards with soldered ASIC are being manufactured and extensive measurements are foreseen in coming weeks. Measurements on socket already show great performances from the ASIC. All performances will be discussed during the oral presentation of the PSIROC ASIC including thorough ENC measurements, dynamic range, TOT, ESD protection against GEM sparks, etc.

3.5. CPROC

3.5.1. Architecture choice

RISC-V is an open-source instruction set architecture (ISA) used to develop custom processors for a wide range of applications, from embedded microcontrollers (MCUs) to application CPUs. Unlike proprietary processor architectures, RISC-V is fully open-source, allowing for greater flexibility in processor design. Originally developed at the University of California, Berkeley, RISC-V represents the fifth generation of processors based on the reduced instruction set computer (RISC) concept. Thanks to its openness and technical advantages, RISC-V has gained significant popularity in recent years. The standard is now maintained by RISC-V International.

The advantage of using the RISC-V standard is gaining access to pre-existing cores and their documentation. For the project the primary criterion was that the cores must be licensed under a free

license. Another important factor was finding a core whose code is written in a language supported by the design tools. The availability of comprehensive documentation was also a critical consideration. To ensure effective design and ease of understanding, the core needed to be up-to-date, well-documented, and actively maintained; having an active community still working on the project is a significant advantage in this context. The extensions available for the core, meaning the code that supports the instructions added by these extensions, were also a factor, though less critical, as support for these extensions can always be added to the core by mimicking existing instructions in the code.

3.5.2. CPU core

PicoRV32 []{a} is the core that has been selected as the foundation for CPROC. It is licensed under the ISC license, meaning it is free and open hardware. Some of its interesting features:

- Small gate count PicoRV32 (750–1,500 LUTs on FPGA, comparable gate count in ASIC)
- Low Power Consumption
- Selectable native memory interface or AXI4-Lite master
- Optional IRQ support (using a simple custom ISA)
- Easy Integration with Custom Peripherals

PicoRV32 is a configurable RV32 core that supports the base sets RV32I and RV32E, as well as the M and C extensions, which are the only extensions considered for the CPROC project.

The entire RTL code is written in Verilog, the community remains very active, and the documentation is both up-to-date and extensive. Additionally, PicoRV32 has served as the base core for several projects, such as the Raven SoC, an ASIC by Efabless using the 180 nm node []{b}, and the Caravel SoC by Google and Efabless []{c}.

The PicoRV32 CPU was originally designed to be used as an auxiliary processor in FPGA designs and ASICs. Due to module compatibility issues, CPROC will use the PicoRV32 variation that incorporates a native memory interface, utilizing an external SPI master for external integration, see Figure 16. As stated by the author on the PicoRV32 Git repository []{a}, its design combines small size and power efficiency. A smaller design will include fewer flip-flops, making it less sensitive to radiation. CPROC is intended to be integrated into ASICs that will operate in radiation-exposed environments.

For CPROC, the choice of PicoRV32 core configuration is made between five different options:

- the Minimum configuration
- the Mul configuration, with only the multiplier activated
- the Mul+Fast configuration, the normal multiplier is replaced by a single-cycle multiplier
- the Mul+Fast+Div configuration, which features both the fast multiplier and division blocks
- the Mul+Div configuration, which instantiates the normal multiplier and the division block

The Minimum configuration; the Mul configuration, with only the multiplier activated; the Mul+Fast configuration, which replaces the normal multiplier with a single-cycle multiplier; the

Figure 16: block diagram of CPROC ASIC

Mul+Fast+Div %configuration, which features both the fast multiplier and division blocks; and finally, the Mul+Div %configuration, which instantiates the normal multiplier along with the division block.

3.5.3. ISA choice

The RISC-V instruction set architecture (ISA) and related specifications are developed, ratified, and maintained by RISC-V International contributing members within the RISC-V International Technical Working Groups. Within the scope of CPROC, certain parameters are already set based on the constraints: we are using the C extension and the E extension to ensure minimal code size and register file footprint, respectively. Since register x0, the "zero register," is constantly set to zero, the E extension provides $15 \times 32 = 480$ registers solely for the register file. IRQs are also enabled, along with the custom IRQ handling offered by PicoRV32, as we want the final SoC to handle external data. The register file takes up to half of the total number of registers in the core's minimum configuration and accounts for 40% of the total core area as shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: area of the different blocks of CPROC

Figure 2. Register file area share with respect to the core, RV32E.

Designing a rad-hard core is far more complex than expected, as the typical method for making radiation-hardened chips at OMEGA involves triplicating every register within the control path, as shown in Figure 18.

Every triplicated register is spaced out in the layout to reduce the likelihood of a Single Event Effect (SEE) impacting all of the registers. A voter is placed at the output of each triplicated register to ensure that the majority value is propagated through the system, thereby auto correcting any faulty register.

In our case, if the register file is not triplicated, there are still 524 registers that could potentially be triplicated in the minimum configuration.

Figure 18: triplicated register example

Concerning the configurations themselves, the minimum configuration is, unsurprisingly, the most compact in terms of footprint, the most efficient in terms of slack, and has the lowest number of registers. It is by far the best option for a highly compact use case and fairly simple calculations that do not involve extensive multiplication or division,

In conclusion, the final configuration chosen for CPROC is the minimum configuration, corresponding to the RV32EC ISA, with 19x32 registers in the register file, including registers for custom IRQ handling. Adding the multiplier is still under consideration, as the trade-off between area and code size could still be interesting.

3.5.4. Design and capabilities

The CPROC digital block diagram is presented in Figure 19. It is partially based on the PicoSoC, a simple SoC design using PicoRV32, developed for the iCE40-HX8K FPGA Breakout Board.

The features are the following :

- A CPU PicoRV32, RV32EC ISA, running at 40MHz
- An internal 8ko SRAM memory (2048 words)
- An external SPI flash W25Q64NE 1.2 V serial NOR flash from Winbond
- SPI, I2C and UART protocol
- 24 General purposes inputs and 16 General purpose outputs
- 4 external programmable IRQ
- A two start address choice

Figure 19: digital block diagram of CPROC

3.5.5. Measurement results

All communication protocols, including I2C, SPI, and UART, have been successfully tested. The microprocessor performs flawlessly in the RISC-V section, with internal memory access writing, reading, and verification functioning as expected. Access to the Winbond flash via SPI has been fully validated for writing, reading, and verification. The CPROC microprocessor consumes 54 mW in idle mode and 74 mW during operation.

Future iterations of the CPROC ASIC could greatly benefit from transitioning to a more advanced process node (e.g., from 130nm to 65nm), which would reduce both design size and power consumption, while enabling the integration of embedded flash memory. Additionally, implementing triplication for the register file will be considered to ensure full radiation hardening of the ASIC.

4. FUTURE PLANS / CONCLUSION / RELATION TO OTHER AIDA-2020 WORK

WP11 proved to be very effective in fostering a community of designers that could share their expertise and gain a more comprehensive view of the challenges posed by future detector systems. The approach of sharing an engineering run for producing several ASICs turned-out to be an optimal balance between the needs of reducing Non-Recurrent Engineering (NRE) costs and of providing integrated circuits really optimized for different applications. This approach should be encouraged in the future. It is likely to be the only to allow the community to use more advanced technology nodes at an affordable cost. All the AIDAinnova work packages benefit from the ASICs developed in WP11 and this legacy will remain strong for the detector R&D activities that will continue after the project termination. The studies done in the 28 nm node had a significant impact in promoting a wider knowledge of this technology across the involved groups. In future initiatives, the paradigm followed in AIDAinnova could be replicated, with the 28 nm taking the role of the reference node for the design of new generation ASICs and encouraging exploratory studies on more scaled nodes. This will be key to understand in detail the benefits these nodes could possibly bring to the implementation of new detector read-out concepts, in context, such as the future hadron colliders, where unprecedented challenges in term of data handling capabilities, speed and radiation hardness will have to be met and completely new readout schemes might be needed.

5. REFERENCES

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
MPW	Multi Project Wafer
NRE	Non-Recurrent Engineering costs
CSA	Charge Sensitive Amplifier
TDC	Time-to-Digital Converter
ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter
PLL	Phase-Locked Loop
DLL	Delayed-Locked Loop
ENC	Equivalent Noise Charge